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Ambassador & Editor

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- DOAJ is a website that lists open access journals and maintained by Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA).
- The project defines open access journals as scientific and scholarly journals that meet high quality standards by exercising peer review or editorial quality control and "use a funding model that does not charge readers or their institutions for access"

No fees to be included in DOAJ database

Required information for inclusion in the DOAJ

Journal Web Site*

- Dedicated website per journal – journal specific web address*
- All journal content centrally available – not spread over various pages
- Do not mimic other journals' website
- Website clear, concise, easy to navigate, transparent, up to date and correct content – high ethical and professional standards
- Language & grammar usage correct, spell check

Journal Web Site*

- Visible links to business information
- Avoid distracting, offensive, irrelevant, moving, blinking advertisements
- Unique identifier (web address) *:
 - Journal level
 - Article metadata level (also DOI)
 - Full text article level (pdf, html, xml, epub)
- ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) *
 - Print ISSN and/or
 - Online ISSN

Journal Content

- Clear journal structure for easier navigation, indexing, discoverability
- Publication date for each article
- Publication year per volume/issue
- Volumes & issues; **5 articles per year**
- **Start & end page number**
- Authors, affiliations, countries, ORCIDs
- Articles arranged in Table of Contents
- Search/Browse option
- Links to Current, Archive/Past Issues

Ownership & Management

- Journal title unique – not confusing/misleading
- Avoid using misleading information
- Each journal unique, journal specific policies
- All business information about journal available from central website for journal - not generic website for publisher

Editorial Office & Editorial Team

- Editor*/Editor-in-Chief/Associate Editor/Co-Editor
- Full names, Affiliations, Countries, Emails*
- Postal address of office
- Contact information: email/telephone

Governing Body

- Editorial Board*/Editorial Advisory Board
- Arts & Humanities allowed editorial review, 2 editors, no editorial board
- Members are experts in field/journal scope → curriculum vitae
- Full names, Affiliations, Countries, Emails*

Author Fees*

- Article Processing Charges (APCs)
- Article Submission Charges
- Manuscript Handling Fees
- Galley Fees, page charges, colour charges, etc.
- Per article (incl. any taxes if applicable) – not per page
- Waiver policy
- Clearly visible for prospective authors – also if no charges apply*

Peer Review Process*

- Advice on individual manuscripts from reviewers/experts in the field who are not part of the journal's editorial staff
- Quality control rigorous
- Process & policies clearly described on journal's web site
- Number of reviewers assigned to review an article
- Editorial/Peer - Blind/Double blind/Open*

Instructions for Authors*

- Detailed style guide
- Description of quality control process (review)
- Copyright information
- Licensing information
- Plagiarism policy
- Instructions on how to submit an article
- Contact email address

Copyright and Licensing

- Licensing means to grant third parties (anyone else except the right holder) the right of using copyright-protected works
- A license is a permission to use a work in specific ways
- Licenses can only be granted by copyright holder
- Copyright holder can be author or publisher

Copyright *

- Clearly described on the website *
- Recommendation:
 - author retains copyright
 - no exclusive publishing rights
 - no transfer of commercial rights

Content Licensing *

- Clearly described on the website *
- Recommendation:
 - licensing terms on all articles, all versions (html, pdf, xml etc.)
 - embedded in article level metadata → in PDF file
 - Creative Commons licensing

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Contradictory Statement

- **Abstract page:**

Copyright (c) 2018 Journal Name

- **Copyright Policy:**

Authors who publish with this journal agree to retain copyright and grant the journal right of first publication with the work simultaneously

Example: Copyright Held by Authors

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Authors grant [Journal Name] a license to publish the article and identify itself as the original publisher.

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Authors are **permitted and encouraged to post their work online** (e.g., in institutional repositories or on their website) prior to and during the submission process, as it can lead to productive exchanges, as well as earlier and greater citation of published work.

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In order to be accepted and published by **[Journal Name]**, author(s) submitting the article manuscript should complete all the review stages. By submitting the manuscript, the author(s) agreed to these following terms:

The copyright of received articles shall be assigned to [Journal Name] as the publisher of the journal. The intended copyright includes the rights to publish articles in various forms (including reprints). [Journal Name] maintain the publishing rights to the published articles.

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Ethics & Malpractice

- Indicate steps to identify & prevent papers where research misconduct occurred
 - Unethical
 - Plagiarism (statement & similarity check tool)
 - Citation manipulation
 - Data falsification/fabrication
- See **COPE Guidelines** in dealing with allegations
<https://publicationethics.org/>

Financial Sustainability

- Revenue sources (author fees, subscriptions, advertising, reprints, institutional support, organizational support)
- Advertising policy, types of ads, decision making on ads, ads linked to content or reader behavior/displayed at random
- Marketing: appropriate, well targeted, unobtrusive

Publishing Schedule

- Clearly indicate periodicity
- **No interruptions ***
- Annually, bi-annually, monthly, bi-monthly, continuous, etc.
- Number of volumes, issues

Access & Usage

- Full text of all content available as Open Access, no delay/embargo*
- How accessible is journal to the rest of the world, harvesters
- Download statistics

Access & Usage

Example DOAJ OA Statement

This is an Open Access journal which means that all content is freely available without charge to the user or his/her institution. Users are allowed to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of the articles, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without asking prior permission from the publisher or the author. This is in accordance with the BOAI definition of Open Access.

DOAJ Seal for Open Access Journals

- **Best practice** recommendations for OA publishing
- Based on 7 criteria relating to accessibility, openness, discoverability, reuse, and authors rights
- All criteria must be met to be awarded the DOAJ Seal
- Note **the seal does not reflect the academic quality of the journal**

The qualifiers for the DOAJ Seal

DOAJ promotes best practice in Open Access publishing. To highlight journals that adhere to best practices, we have created the 'DOAJ Seal for Open Access Journals'.

The qualifiers for the Seal highlight features related to accessibility, openness, discoverability, reuse and author rights and have nothing to do with **the scholarly quality of the papers published**.

To qualify for the Seal the journal must:

1. have an **archival arrangement in place** with an external party (Question 25). 'No policy in place' does not qualify for the Seal.
2. provide **permanent identifiers** in the papers published (Question 28). 'None' does not qualify for the Seal.
3. provide **article level metadata** to DOAJ (Question 29). 'No' or failure to provide metadata within 3 months do not qualify for the Seal.
4. embed **machine-readable CC licensing information** in article level metadata (Question 45). 'No' does not qualify for the Seal.
5. allow **reuse and remixing of content** in accordance with a CC BY, CC BY-SA or CC BY-NC license (Question 47). If CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND, 'No' or 'Other' is selected the journal will not qualify for the Seal.
6. have a **deposit policy registered** in a deposit policy directory. (Question 51) 'No' does not qualify for the Seal.
7. allow **the author to hold the copyright without restrictions**. (Question 52) 'No' does not qualify for the Seal.

One cannot apply for the Seal. The Seal is awarded based on the information provided in the application. If you have any questions about any of the qualifiers, contact us.

Digital Archiving Arrangements

- To ensure long-term availability and preservation of journal content
- Key archiving services: LOCKSS, CLOCKSS, Portico
- PKP-LOCKSS
- Relawan Jurnal Indonesia (RJI) Archive
- National libraries' digital preservation services
- PubMed Central
- Institutional servers or repositories do not qualify

Digital Archiving & Preservation

- Electronic backup
 - Cloud, disk, server, tapes, etc
- Preservation – Keepers' Registry (<https://thekeepers.org/>)
 - PubMed Central
 - Portico
 - Open Journal Systems (OJS) – PKP Private LOCKSS network deposited in CLOCKSS

Permanent Identifiers

- To ensure articles may continue to be found even when URLs change, avoid “link rot”
- Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
- Handle
- ARK

Metadata Supply

- To provide greater visibility and discoverability of journal content
- Provide article-level metadata to DOAJ
- **Within 3 months of acceptance**
- Data can be supplied via XML file or using API

Creative Commons License

- To allow generous reuse and remixing of content
- 4 of the 6 CC licenses qualify for the Seal
- CC BY, CC BY-SA, CC BY-NC, CC BY-NC-SA
- The most restrictive CC licenses do not qualify
- CC BY-ND and CC BY-NC-ND do not allow remixing and creation of derivative products

<https://creativecommons.org/>

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CC BY-NC-SA

CC BY-ND

CC BY-NC-ND

CC BY-NC

Machine-readable License Information

- To ensure users know and understand what they are permitted to do with the content
- Embed license data in article-level metadata
- Any of 4 Creative Commons licenses

Article level CCL

South African
CRIME QUARTERLY

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Home > No 56 (2016) > Lancaster

Risky localities: Exploring a methodology for measuring socio-economic characteristics of high murder areas
Lizette Lancaster, Ellen Kamman

Abstract

Every day on average, more than 49 people are murdered in South Africa. A better understanding of the demographics of locations with high murder and other crime rates could assist in the development of effective initiatives to effectively reduce our murder rate. It provides the foundations on which to build research into the impact of social cohesion on violence reduction. This article explores the hypothesis that the risk for murder is associated with certain demographic characteristics of particular locations. This paper proposes a method to analyse the demographic characteristics of police precincts in relation to the murder rate for that police precinct. It provides an explanation of the method used and a summary of initial results. The paper concludes with a discussion on the benefits of this research approach and considerations for future research as well as the need for more indepth analysis on social cohesion.

Keywords

murder, crime analysis, crime statistics, crime hotspots

Full Text:
PDF

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17159/2413-3108/2016/v0n56a51>

Refbacks

- There are currently no refbacks.

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- Transfer of commercial rights to the publisher do not qualify

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